

ANALYSIS ON DATA WITH TRIALINDEX 11-20

Number of trials per stimulus mode					
	0	100	140	180	Total
None	34	-	-	-	34
AudioOnly	-	30	33	30	93
VisualsOnly	-	24	27	31	82
Both	-	31	25	31	87
Total	34	85	85	92	296

Stimuli type and performance

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variable: correctNormalized

ANOVA correctNormalized~stimulusTrial	
F	p
1.61	0.187

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasStimulusTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
1.0008818	0.9896268	0.58707	0.5605

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasVisualTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
1.0006579	0.9981666	0.23468	0.8146

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasAudioTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
1.0020358	0.9957922	0.5745	0.5662

Stimuli tempo and performance

Parameter: tempo | Variable: correctNormalized | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo	
F	p
0.306	0.874

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]	
F	p
1.212	0.302

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]	
F	p
0.223	0.8

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterBOTH]				
F	p			
3.693	0.029			
TukeyHSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
140-100	0.0021669	-0.0547364	0.0590703	0.9954592
180-100	0.0549160	0.0011473	0.1086847	0.0441984
180-140	0.0527490	-0.0041543	0.1096525	0.0749964

Stimuli type and time estimation

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception)

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~stimulusTrial	
F	p
1.471	0.222

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasStimulusTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
-0.0011148	0.0792334	-1.5604	0.1267

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasVisualTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
-0.0093791	0.0313932	-1.3607	0.1749

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasAudioTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.0104150	0.0045443	0.19766	0.8435

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~stimulusTrial	
F	p
0.657	0.579

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasStimulusTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.1812827	0.2192312	-1.0694	0.2915

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasVisualTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.1765853	0.1976929	-1.04	0.2985

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasAudioTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.1844646	0.1874681	-0.15263	0.8788

Stimuli tempo and time estimation

Parameter: tempo | Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception) | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo	
F	p
1.61	0.187

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]	
F	p
1.753	0.179

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]	
F	p
0.423	0.657

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterBOTH]	
F	p
0.807	0.449

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo	
F	p
0.96	0.412

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]	
F	p
0.91	0.406

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]				
F	p			
2.399	0.0974			
TukeyHSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
140-100	-0.0832855	-0.1788551	0.0122840	0.001874
180-100	-0.0662405	-0.1588631	0.0263820	0.2084650
180-140	0.0170449	-0.0726304	0.1067203	0.8927609

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterBOTH]	
F	p
1.013	0.367

Stimuli type and time judgment

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variable: reportedSpeedPerception

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~classes			
chi-2	df	p	
15.639	3	0.001345	

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasStimulusTrial			
W	p		
6216	8.939e-05		
paired WILCOXON			
mean Has	mean Not		
3.446565	2.705882		

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasAudioTrial			
W	p		
11366	0.1788		
paired WILCOXON			
mean Has	mean Not		
3.422222	3.267241		

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasVisualTrial			
W	p		
12158	0.04103		
paired WILCOXON			
mean Has	mean Not		
3.473373	3.212598		

paired WILCOXON			
AudioOnly	Both	None	
Both	0.8139	-	
None	0.0015	0.0015	-
VisualsOnly	0.8139	0.8139	0.0008

Stimuli tempo and time judgment

Parameter: tempo | Variable: reportedSpeedPerception | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo			
chi-2	df	p	
18.031	3	0.0004334	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
chi-2	df	p
0.57733	2	0.7493

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
chi-2	df	p
0.29753	2	0.8618

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterBOTH]		
chi-2	df	p
2.3693	2	0.3059

paired WILCOXON			
0	100	140	
100	0.01392	-	-
140	0.00112	0.35195	-
180	0.00012	0.17561	0.62453

Correlations time judgment - estimation - performance

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), reportedSpeedPerception, correctNormalized

PEARSON deltaTimePerception~correctNormalized			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.18648313	0.0402917	-0.0740529	0.2039

PEARSON abs(deltaTimePerception)~correctNormalized			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1299692	0.0979807	-0.0162048	0.7813

SPEARMAN deltaTimePerception~reportedSpeedPerception			
rho	p		
-0.2357209	4.2e-05		

SPEARMAN abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedSpeedPerception			
rho	p		
0.2146358	0.0001988		

SPEARMAN correctNormalized~reportedSpeedPerception			
rho	p		
0.1676492	0.00382		

Confounding effects of fatigue

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), reportedSpeedPerception, correctNormalized, reportedFatigue

ANOVA correctNormalized~reportedFatigue			
F	p		
0.306	0.874		

Anova deltaTimePerception~reportedFatigue			
F	p		
0.9	0.464		

Anova abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedFatigue			
F	p		
1.35	0.251		

Spearman correctNormalized~reportedFatigue			
rho	p		
0.0212115	0.7163		

Spearman deltaTimePerception~reportedFatigue			
rho	p		
0.0098673	0.8658		

Spearman abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedFatigue			
rho	p		
0.0731379	0.2096		

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~reportedFatigue			
rho	p		
0.3099189	5.206e-08		

Confounding effects of trial index

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), correctNormalized, trialIndex

Pearson correctNormalized~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.14476355	0.0830253	-0.0312751	0.592

Pearson deltaTimePerception~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0088663	0.2166496	0.1052445	0.0706

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1407688	0.0870736	-0.0272008	0.6412